

1 **A workflow for quality control in surface texture analysis applied to teeth and**
2 **tools**

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13 **Keywords**

14 Dental microwear texture analysis

15 Good-practice

16 Non-measured points

17 Outliers

18 Quantitative artefact microwear analysis

19 Use-wear analysis

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22 **Short title**

23 Quality control in surface texture analysis for teeth and tools

24

25 **Abstract**

26 Quantification and automation represent important methodological developments in
27 dental microwear analysis and in artifact microwear (use-wear) analysis in order to
28 address the issues of subjectivity and reproducibility of the traditional methods,
29 increase discrimination power, and improve pattern recognition. However, automatic
30 and quantitative methods (dental microwear texture and quantitative artifact
31 microwear analyses) require high-quality data to work with. Surface data acquired with
32 confocal microscopy can reach incredible levels of accuracy and resolution; yet, they are
33 not without issues. In this paper, in an approach similar to quality control in industry, I
34 propose a good-practice workflow for controlling the quality of the acquired and
35 processed 3D data (height maps). I also suggest tools to deal with some of the issues
36 commonly encountered. This workflow should be applied routinely to every height map
37 after acquisition and processing, so that only high-quality height maps are analyzed. In
38 turn, the systematic quality control of the 3D data improves the robustness of the
39 quantitative results and of their interpretations.

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41 **1. Introduction**

42 Surface texture analysis has many applications, most of them being industrial (e.g.
43 Brown et al., 2018; Leach, 2013; Todhunter et al., 2017). Such analysis has also been
44 applied for almost two decades to the surfaces of modern and fossil teeth (dental
45 microwear texture analysis, DMTA; see reviews by Calandra and Merceron, 2016;
46 DeSantis, 2016; Green and Croft, 2018; Schulz-Kornas et al., 2020; Ungar, 2015), as well
47 as to those of archaeological / experimental tools and artifacts (quantitative artifact
48 microwear analysis, QAMA, also known as quantitative use-wear analysis; see reviews
49 by Calandra et al., 2019a; Marreiros et al., 2020; Stemp et al., 2016). Quantification and
50 automation, in the form of DMTA and QAMA, are seen as major aspects of the solution to
51 the issues of subjectivity and to the lack of repeatability / reproducibility in dental
52 microwear and traceological analyses, as well as to improve discrimination power and
53 pattern recognition (e.g. Evans et al., 2014a; Ibáñez et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2006; Stemp
54 et al., 2016; Ungar et al., 2008, 2003). While quantification and automation surely are
55 important parts of the solution, they can only fulfill their potential if the methods are
56 applied to high-quality data. It is therefore important to check the quality of the data, in
57 this case of the height maps representing the sample's surface topography, before
58 analysis. Many industrial processes include some sort of quality control in their
59 workflows, i.e. checking whether the production or function of a part fulfills the
60 requirements (e.g. Baqueta et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2018; Rebsamen et al., 2010). Surface
61 texture analysis is actually often applied as a means for quality control (e.g. Brown et al.,
62 2018; Leach, 2013; Todhunter et al., 2017). However, the concept of quality control is
63 neither widely known nor applied in paleontology and archaeology.

64 The majority of 3D surface texture data on teeth and artifacts has been acquired using
65 confocal microscopes. In DMTA, most recent studies use systems produced by Sensofar

66 (the Leica DCM8 being the same machine) (e.g. Hernando et al., 2022; Merceron et al.,
67 2021b; Ungar et al., 2020), although other confocal microscopes are used too (Keyence
68 VK-series, e.g. Aiba et al., 2019; Kubo et al., 2017; NanoFocus μ surf systems, e.g. Schulz-
69 Kornas et al., 2019; Winkler et al., 2019). In QAMA, the Sensofar systems are also used
70 (e.g. Díaz Bonilla et al., 2020; Ibáñez et al., 2019; Macdonald et al., 2019; Rosso et al.,
71 2017) but alongside other confocal microscopes (Olympus LEXT series, e.g. Evans et al.,
72 2014b; Evans and Donahue, 2008; Evans and Macdonald, 2011; Werner, 2018; Zeiss
73 LSM 800, Pedergnana et al., 2020a, 2020b). Other imaging techniques have been applied
74 as well, for example focus variation (e.g. Bestwick et al., 2019; Gill et al., 2014;
75 Macdonald, 2014; Macdonald et al., 2020; Pfleging et al., 2019; Purnell et al., 2017;
76 Stemp et al., 2019), interferometry (Borel et al., 2021; Dumont, 1982; Merceron et al.,
77 2014; Souron et al., 2015) and atomic force microscopy (Faulks et al., 2011; Kimball et
78 al., 2017, 1995). While confocal microscopy seems to be very appropriate to acquire 3D
79 surface data from dental and artifact surfaces, the resulting height maps are not without
80 issues. Every analyst has noticed that the resulting height maps often contain positive or
81 negative outliers, also called spikes (e.g. Schulz et al., 2013; Ungar et al., 2003). These
82 result from incorrect calculations of height due to aberrant light reflection / refraction,
83 which usually occur on steep slopes (Artigas, 2011; Stemp et al., 2019). Because these
84 spikes can have very high or low heights (i.e. well above or below the “true” surface),
85 their presence can greatly influence the results of the quantitative analysis, especially
86 the values of the height parameters (e.g. Sa , Sz and $S5p$ of the ISO 25178-2 norm;
87 International Organization for Standardization, 2021). These issues stem mostly from
88 the properties of the samples’ surfaces: dental enamel and dentine for DMTA, and a
89 variety of natural rocks (e.g. flint, quartzite, obsidian and basalt), organic materials (e.g.
90 bone and antler), as well as human-made materials (e.g. metals and ceramics), for

91 QAMA. The surfaces of these materials range from very smooth to very rough and from
92 opaque to transparent, have shallow to steep slopes, and come in all colors.
93 Many acquisition settings can and do influence the quality of the resulting height map
94 (e.g. the numerical aperture of the objective; Calandra et al., 2019b), but here I will focus
95 on how to check and validate (i.e. *control*) the quality of the acquired and processed
96 height maps before running the quantitative analysis.

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99 **2. Proposed workflow**

100 The workflow for quality control in surface texture analysis that I propose (Fig. 1) can
101 be split into three main steps: (1) acquire the height map, (2) clean the height map
102 digitally and (3) fix issues, if possible. The quality should be controlled after each step
103 (Table 1).

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Figure 1. Proposed workflow for quality control in surface texture analysis applied to DMTA and QAMA.

Step	Issues	Diagnostic features & tools	Potential solutions
1. Acquire	ROI cannot be imaged due to hardware or sample constraints	Risk for the sample and/or hardware	Search new ROI, select an objective with a higher working distance or mold the ROI
	Heterogeneous, translucent or reflective samples/ROI	NMP and/or spikes	Search new ROI or mold the sample's surface
	Slopes too steep relative to the objective's NA	NMP and/or spikes along slopes	Tilt the sample to position the ROI horizontally or select an objective with a higher NA
	Overhangs not imaged		Tilt the sample to position the ROI horizontally or choose another technique (e.g. CT)
Under- or over-exposure	NMP and/or spikes and/or noise	Adjust light settings	
2. Clean	Particles of dust, dirt or contaminants on the surface	2D and 3D views	<i>Retouch</i> or <i>Threshold</i> operators
	Large outliers/spikes on the height map	Range of the Z color scale in 2D and 3D views	<i>Threshold</i> or <i>Remove outliers</i> operators, morphological filters with thresholding and surface subtraction, or spatial filters
	Small outliers/spikes on the height map	Zooming in and tilting the 3D view	
	Measurement noise		Gaussian filters or <i>Remove measurement noise</i> option of the <i>Remove outliers</i> operator
3. Fix	Too many missing points	NMP ratio in the Identity Card	<i>Extract area</i> operator or combine several acquisitions

111 Table 1. Summary of issues and tools to recognize them during quality control. Potential
112 solutions to these issues are also summarized. NA = numerical aperture, NMP = non-
113 measured points, ROI = region of interest.

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116 2.1 Acquire

117 I argue it is important to invest adequate time for the acquisition itself. Even if some
118 issues can be fixed later (see sections 2.2-2.3), the fixes cannot compensate for a good
119 acquisition. Additionally, processing and analyzing high-quality data will be easier, and
120 will therefore require less time from the analyst.

121 While beyond the scope of this paper, proper sample preparation and cleaning are pre-
122 requisites to a high-quality acquisition. Every particle of dust/dirt, contaminants,
123 coatings, consolidants, etc. will be part of the sample's surface to acquire. Therefore, the
124 samples' surfaces should be carefully cleaned physically before acquisition, although
125 how to best clean artifacts is still a debated topic (e.g. Macdonald et al., 2018;
126 Macdonald and Evans, 2014a, 2014b; Mateo-Lomba et al., 2022; Pedergrana et al.,
127 2020a; Valtierra et al., 2022; Williams and Doyle, 2010). Furthermore, cleaning will
128 remove or destroy residues that can be very informative about contact materials, so
129 residue analysis should be performed before cleaning (e.g. Rots et al., 2016).

130 The first aspect of the acquisition is the choice of the acquisition system (mostly
131 confocal microscopes; see e.g. Leach, 2011a; Schulz et al., 2013), its hardware (e.g.
132 objective) and the acquisition settings (e.g. Artigas, 2011; Calandra et al., 2019b; Leach,
133 2011b). However, I argue that once the equipment (microscope, objectives, software)
134 has been purchased, the analyst usually has access to only this equipment, even if
135 another would be more appropriate for studying the samples. Analysts are therefore
136 constrained by the capabilities of the pieces of equipment to which they have access. It
137 is therefore all the more important to choose the acquisition settings carefully.

138 It is also crucial that the region of interest (ROI) lies horizontally under the
139 microscope's objective, so that the light beam hits the ROI at a right angle (Artigas,
140 2011). Even though confocal microscopes acquire 3D data, light travels in a straight

141 path, so overhangs cannot be imaged (but see Macdonald et al., 2022 for the use of CT
142 scanning). A tilted ROI will increase the number and size of areas that light cannot reach
143 (Fig. 2). Additionally, steep slopes are difficult to image because objectives are limited in
144 the steepness of the local slopes that can be imaged, depending on their numerical
145 apertures (Artigas, 2011; Calandra et al., 2019b; Leach, 2011b). On archaeological
146 artifacts (or their experimental equivalents), positioning a ROI horizontally often means
147 tilting the sample (see e.g. fig. 1e of Pedergrana et al., 2020b, and fig. 4b of Pedergrana
148 et al. 2020c). A horizontal ROI has the useful side-effect of being faster to image because
149 less images per stack will be acquired thanks to the smaller height range between the
150 lowest and highest points.

151 For heterogeneous, translucent, and/or reflective samples, I suggest to mold the
152 sample's surface, as it may improve the quality of the acquired height map. Silicone
153 molding materials commonly used in paleontology and archaeology are opaque and
154 homogeneous, and can be imaged directly with confocal microscopes (e.g. Merceron et
155 al., 2016; Schulz et al., 2010). While their long-term durability is still unknown, they
156 have been shown to reproduce the surface accurately (Goodall et al., 2015; Macdonald
157 et al., 2018; Mhlbachler et al., 2019; Rodriguez et al., 2009; Rodriguez and Bartlett,
158 2011; Schunk et al., 2022).

159 In any case, it is important to pay attention to the light settings for acquisition, as over-
160 or under-exposure will reduce the quality of the acquisition (Artigas, 2011). The sample
161 should receive as much light as possible without being overexposed in order to increase
162 the signal-to-noise ratio.

163 Finally, it might not be possible to image every ROI on the sample. Some ROIs might be
164 too tilted relative to the sample's shape so that it is impossible to position it horizontally
165 without touching the objective, others might be too deep so that the objective cannot

166 reach it without touching the sample, etc. In some cases, it might therefore be necessary
167 to select another ROI or an objective with a longer working distance (e.g. Schulz et al.,
168 2010). The selection of the ROI should also consider issues of preservation (Böhm et al.,
169 2019; Caux et al., 2018; Galland et al., 2019; Martisius et al., 2020; Weber et al., 2022,
170 2021; Werner, 2018) and representativeness (Borel et al., 2021; Evans et al., 2014b;
171 Marreiros et al., 2020), as well as cleanliness (see above).

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175 **Figure 2.** Schematic diagram showing the influence of the tilt of the region of interest
176 (ROI) on the 3D acquisition. **(a)** When the ROI is positioned horizontally, the light rays
177 (orange arrows) from the light source (orange cylinder) can reach all points of the
178 surface, even the deepest pits. **(b)** When the ROI is tilted, the light rays cannot reach
179 some areas, resulting in non-measured or aberrant points (black area) on the resulting
180 height maps. Modified from Calandra (2011).

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183 Once the height map has been acquired, its quality must be checked (Table 1). I believe
184 that quality control is easy and fast to perform, for example using the software
185 Mountains by Digital Surf. Particles of dust, dirt or contaminants that were present on
186 the sample's surface during acquisition will be part of the height map, and therefore, of
187 the analysis. They can be identified in the 2D and 3D views (studies "Pseudo-color view"
188 and "3D view", respectively, in Mountains), and can be deleted manually (see section
189 2.2); if not, the height map should be re-acquired or excluded from analysis (see section
190 2.3)(e.g. Schulz et al., 2010).

191 Outliers are single points or very small areas that stand well above or below the local
192 surface. Outliers should be removed before analysis (see section 2.2). The presence of
193 large outliers (high/low spikes) is easily noticeable by looking at the Z scale: if the
194 height map does not show the whole color range (e.g. mostly blue areas), then spikes
195 are likely to be present. After deleting these spikes (see section 2.2), the whole color
196 scale will be visible on the 2D and 3D views. Even if the full color scale is visible on the
197 height map, smaller outliers might be present. While sometimes difficult to visualize in
198 the 2D view, such outliers/spikes become clearly visible when zooming in and tilting the
199 3D view to view the height map from the side (Fig. 3a). The height map should be
200 displayed at full resolution. Amplification of the Z-axis relative to the X/Y-scales can also
201 help (this is one of the settings of the "3D view" study in Mountains). Very small spikes
202 usually result from measurement noise, introduced by the confocal microscope and the
203 environment during acquisition; it occurs with any system (Artigas, 2011).

204 The non-measured point (NMP) ratio, i.e. the number of non-measured points divided
205 by the total number of points (pixels), could be used as a simple proxy for quality. The
206 NMP ratio is part of the "Identity Card" in Mountains (e.g. Fig. 3). There is no agreed-
207 upon threshold; for example, some authors exclude height maps having more than 5 %

208 NMP (e.g. Schulz et al., 2010, 2013). The threshold might need to be adapted to the
209 sample properties; for example, very rough surface like those of quartzite are usually
210 much more difficult to acquire (and have therefore more NMPs) than those of flint (see
211 e.g. Pedergrana et al., 2020b). The distribution of NMPs is also important: large areas of
212 NMP should be avoided, while a few evenly distributed NMPs are unlikely to influence
213 the results (François Blateyron, pers. comm. 2021). If NMPs are concentrated in specific
214 areas, I recommend to acquire a new height map at a slightly different position, to
215 extract areas of the height map outside of these NMPs, or to combine several
216 acquisitions (see section 2.3).

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 220 **Figure 3.** Controlling a height map **(a)** before and **(b)** after cleaning by removing
 221 outliers ($> 80^\circ$ slope). Notice that neither the XY sizes (in μm and in pixels) nor the XYZ
 222 resolutions have changed due to cleaning. The Z size has changed due to the removal of
 223 outliers; this is expected and actually the desired behavior. All z-scales have been fixed
 224 ($Z\text{-range} = 26.41 \mu\text{m}$) for comparisons. NMPs are shown in red. Height maps are
 225 displayed with the Viridis color palette (see Crameri et al., 2020). The Mountains
 226 document from where the images come from is available on Zenodo
 227 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034213>). The flint surface was acquired by Calandra
 228 et al. (2019b).

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231 2.2 Clean (digitally)

232 Three types of defects should be removed before analysis: particles that are deposited
233 on the sample's surface, spikes/outliers, and measurement noise (Table 1). These
234 defects should be removed from the height maps, or the height maps should be
235 excluded from the analysis.

236 Even when the samples' surfaces have been physically cleaned as part of the sample
237 preparation protocol (see section 2.1), some particles can still be present. Particles can
238 be digitally erased manually from the 2D or 3D view (operator "Retouch" in Mountains;
239 e.g. Scott et al., 2006), although any manual alteration of the height map is necessarily
240 subjective and might significantly change the results in non-reproducible ways.

241 Alternatively and reproducibly, very large (and high) particles can also be deleted
242 automatically with a thresholding operator (operator "Threshold" in Mountains; e.g.
243 Scott et al., 2006).

244 There is no standard way for deleting outliers. Arman et al. (2016), for example, apply
245 in the Mountains software both a thresholding operator (0.1 to 99.9 %) and the
246 operator "Remove outliers" (slope > 80°; Fig. 3b). Merceron et al. (2016) combine
247 mathematical morphological filters with thresholding and surface subtraction (with the
248 operators "Morphological filter", "Threshold" and "Subtract surfaces"; see their fig. S2).
249 The procedure of Schulz et al. (2013) and Ibáñez et al. (2019) applies a spatial filter
250 (operator "Spatial filter" in Mountains), which also removes measurement noise (see
251 below).

252 The influence of measurement noise on the quantitative results is likely to be minimal
253 because the variations in surface textures due to noise can be expected to be smaller
254 than those resulting from wear processes. Nevertheless, I argue it should be considered
255 good practice to exclude noise from the analysis. Indeed, noise blurs the signal, so

256 removing it will increase the strength of the signal. In general, noise is removed by
257 band-pass filters such as Gaussian filters (operator “Metrological filter” in
258 Mountains)(e.g. Arman et al., 2016; Pedergrana et al., 2020b; Schulz et al., 2013),
259 though there is no pre-defined cut-off for DMTA and QAMA because this is dependent
260 on the acquisition system and settings (e.g. XY-resolution). The operator “Remove
261 outliers” in Mountains also has an option to remove measurement noise (Arman et al.,
262 2016).

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264 The cleaned height maps should be controlled again for quality, just like the acquired
265 height maps have been: 3D view, zooming in and NMP ratio (see section 2.1, Fig. 3 and
266 Table 1).

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268 2.3 Fix

269 There are potentially many issues that an analyst might want to fix on a height map, but
270 in this section, I focus on one proxy for quality: the NMP ratio. High NMP ratios are
271 sometimes measured on acquired height maps, but they more often occur on cleaned
272 height maps. I propose two tools to reduce the number of NMPs on a height map (Fig. 1,
273 Table 1).

274 The first tool is to extract a smaller area from a height map (operator “Extract area” in
275 Mountains). If the extracted area is chosen as to avoid NMP-rich areas, this option can
276 greatly reduce the NMP ratio of the resulting height map (Fig. 4). This method is
277 applicable at any stage before analysis and does not require a new acquisition.

278 However, this method has several drawbacks that are important to consider. First,
279 while the area can be extracted automatically at a given position, this is unlikely to
280 extract a low-NMP area from every height map; a manual selection is probably

281 necessary. This leads to the second problem: the representativeness and selection bias
282 introduced by this manual selection. This selection bias adds another layer of
283 subjectivity to the original selection bias in choosing the location on the sample's
284 surface. Additionally, smaller surfaces are necessarily less representative of a sample
285 than larger ones, which could explain why larger surfaces seem to hold more
286 discrimination power (Ibáñez et al., 2019; Ramdarshan et al., 2017). Lastly, areas
287 extracted from larger height maps have less pixels; if these areas become too small, they
288 might not contain enough pixels to run the analysis. There is currently no standard
289 threshold in terms of number of pixels for a meaningful analysis; the analyst should
290 decide on the minimum number of pixels. This issue is well-known in DMTA on rodent
291 teeth. For example, areas $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ at $0.16 \mu\text{m}$ XY-resolution (Calandra et al., 2016a)
292 or $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ at $0.13 \mu\text{m}$ XY-resolution (Calandra et al., 2016b) were analyzed on vole
293 teeth because the enamel bands are very thin. The resulting numbers of analyzed pixels,
294 62×62 and 115×115 respectively, were very small and probably insufficient but no
295 alternative (see below) was available. Winkler et al. (2019), on guinea pigs' teeth,
296 analyzed areas $60 \times 60 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a pixel size of $0.16 \mu\text{m}$, resulting in 375×375 pixels
297 per height map. This issue also occurs in QAMA, for example when analyzing samples
298 with very small and discontinuous polished areas, such as on quartzite surfaces. For
299 example, Pedergrana et al. (2020b) analyzed areas $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ with pixels 0.25×0.25
300 μm^2 , i.e. 201×201 pixels per height map. This issue can be avoided during the
301 acquisition through a reduction of the pixel size either by choosing a higher-
302 magnification objective or by increasing the optical zoom factor (to reduce the field-of-
303 view), or by increasing the number of pixels (Artigas, 2011). Several smaller
304 acquisitions can then be stitched together to increase the acquired area, in-turn
305 improving the representativeness.

306
 307 **Figure 4.** Fixing a height map via area extraction. **(a)** Cleaned height map (Fig. 3b) and
 308 **(b)** extracted area. Notice that, as expected, the XYZ sizes changed, but not the XYZ
 309 resolutions. See legend of Fig. 3 for further information on scales, colors and source of
 310 the height maps. See Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034213> for details.

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314 The second tool to reduce the number of NMP is to combine several acquisitions. The
315 principle is as follows: assuming that some of the NMPs are randomly distributed or at
316 least not all at the exact same positions, it is expected that for the majority of points,
317 every point will be acquired correctly on at least one of the cleaned height maps. In
318 other words, the combined height map will contain NMPs only for the points where all
319 cleaned height maps had NMPs. This method requires several acquisitions of the same
320 ROI. This is achieved easily during the initial acquisition by acquiring several times in a
321 row without moving the sample or without changing settings, but it is much more
322 difficult to do afterwards because relocating the ROI can be challenging (but see
323 Calandra et al., 2019c; Ibáñez and Mazzucco, 2021). In the Mountains software, the
324 procedure is performed in three steps: (1) combine the cleaned height maps (Fig. 5a)
325 into a series of surfaces (operator “Build series of surfaces”; Fig. 5b), (2) shift (i.e. align)
326 them to make sure that they all represent the exact same surface (operator “Shift
327 surfaces”; Fig. 5c), and (3) extract the mean surface of the series (operator “Extract
328 surface”; Fig. 5d). The mean of the heights from the height maps will be calculated for
329 each pixel. NMPs will be ignored, so that one measurement per pixel is enough to fill-in
330 the mean height map. Calculating the mean height map will also help reducing the
331 measurement noise (see section 2.1) (Artigas, 2011). These operations require the
332 optional module “4D Surface Change”. Some, if not all, acquisition software packages
333 allow the automatic acquisition of several images and averaging of the acquisitions (e.g.
334 Sensofar’s SensoSCAN or Zeiss’ ZEN blue). These methods are easier to implement than
335 the workflow in Mountains. Nevertheless, it seems that the latter is more powerful and
336 accurate (Hala Alarashi, pers. comm. 2022). This could be due to the alignment of the
337 surfaces in Mountains. The more acquisitions, the better (up to a certain point, see

338 Artigas, 2011); I suggest three acquisitions, as I have found it to usually represent a
339 good compromise between time and quality.
340 It is important to note that filling in NMPs digitally in the height maps does not solve the
341 issues presented above: it interpolates the surface to artificially fill the holes with
342 calculated height values, which is not recommended for surface texture measurements
343 (e.g. Helmlí, 2011). Nevertheless, filling NMPs can be an important processing step too,
344 as some parameters cannot be calculated on incomplete height maps. The operator "Fill
345 NM points" can be used in Mountains for this purpose (e.g. Arman et al., 2016) but other
346 algorithms might perform better (Francisco et al., 2020). I recommend to fill NMPs only
347 if the NMP ratio is low (e.g. < 5 %) and if NMPs are relatively evenly distributed across
348 the surface (see section 2.1).

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350 Eventually, the output height maps should be controlled for quality one last time before
351 analysis: 3D view, zooming in and NMP ratio before filling in NMPs (see section 2.1, Fig.
352 3 and Table 1).

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360 **Figure 5.** Fixing a height map by combining several acquisitions. **(a)** Three outlier-free
361 height maps with their respective NMP ratios; they were acquired by clicking three
362 times in a row on “acquire”. **(b)** The series of surfaces built from the three height maps.
363 **(c)** The shifted series; the shifting was performed automatically and the intersection
364 was kept. Because the height maps were acquired in a row, the height maps were
365 aligned with very minimal offset and rotation that are not visible on those images (see
366 Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034213> for details). **(d)** The mean surface of
367 the series and its identity card. Note that the NMP ratio is much lower in (d) than in (a).
368 Notice also that the XY sizes differ slightly, but that the XY resolutions are identical to
369 the height maps in (a) (see Figs 3b or 4a). The change in XY sizes is due to the shifting in
370 (c). See legend of Fig. 3 for further information on scales, colors and source of the height
371 maps.

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374 **3. Discussion and conclusions**

375 I believe that many analysts are aware of most of these issues and have developed ways
376 to deal with them. But few of them have published their experiences and solutions. As
377 such, even if some of this knowledge has been shared by other means (internal
378 trainings, workshops, conferences, etc.), every analyst must at least partly
379 independently gain this knowledge. This also implies that there is currently no
380 standard, guideline or best-practice for DMTA or QAMA. This proposed workflow is a
381 first stepping stone toward filling this gap. Far from being a standard, it should rather
382 be seen as a good-practice at this moment. As such, it will have to be expanded,
383 developed, detailed and edited as DMTA/QAMA analysts incorporate quality control in
384 their daily routines. It will be especially important to agree on methods to control, clean
385 and fix the height maps. For this purpose, a cross-disciplinary community effort will not
386 only allow numerous researchers to contribute with their perhaps unique experiences,
387 but will also provide the fertile ground for the planted seed to germinate and grow.

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389 While this workflow is still only in its first version, it highlights a few key aspects of
390 quality control relevant for DMTA/QAMA:

391 1) Some issues that occur during acquisition can be corrected during processing. Others
392 cannot, but in these cases, I argue it is preferable to exclude the surfaces from the
393 analysis. In any case, these issues can only be identified if the analyst actively controls
394 the quality of the surfaces before analysis.

395 2) Many studies rely on templates to process and analyze all surfaces in batches. This
396 means that the analysis is applied directly, whether the surface is of good enough
397 quality or not. Nevertheless, it remains important to check every surface before and
398 after processing. In other words, in my view, using templates does not negate the

399 importance of quality control. Indeed, what works on one surface might not work on
400 another, even if the two surfaces are similar.

401 3) Quality control requires some time-investment. Still, I argue it should not be
402 neglected: it is better to spend the time at the beginning rather than noticing the low
403 quality later (e.g. during the review of the manuscript), which would require much more
404 time to alleviate the problems. Even if the low quality does not change the results, it is
405 impossible to know as long as the low-quality results are not compared to the high-
406 quality ones. In other words, I believe it is on average faster to do it right from the
407 beginning.

408 4) Quality control is important for the analyst, but the process should also be made
409 available to other researchers, also in order to improve the good-practice. Many data
410 can be shared to clarify the process: non-measured point ratios of each cleaned height
411 map (e.g. as a CSV file in supplementary material), visual inspection of the surfaces (e.g.
412 photo-simulations and false-color views; Appendix 3 of Merceron et al., 2021a), the
413 whole processing workflow for each surface including non-measured point ratios and
414 visual inspections in MNT and/or PDF formats (e.g. Pedergrana et al., 2020b), and/or
415 acquired or cleaned surfaces as SUR files or as part of the MNT documents. All
416 acquisition settings should also be shared (Calandra et al., 2019b). The many free online
417 repositories (e.g. Zenodo, Open Science Framework, Figshare) make this possible and
418 easy.

419 5) Quality control is essential to ensure the robustness of the results and, in turn, of
420 their interpretations. High-tech pieces of equipment are wonderful tools that can
421 deliver new data to address existing questions and to open new doors, but they have
422 limitations, too. In my opinion, it is the role of the analyst to control whether the

423 acquisition and analysis have been performed appropriately, according to the material
424 and goal(s) of the study.

425

426 To conclude, as Lawrence H. Keeley wrote almost 50 years ago: “There is also no getting
427 around the fact that microwear studies are painstaking and time consuming, and
428 demand tedious attention to technique – to shrug this off or to use technical shortcuts
429 purely in the interests of time will in the long run prove disastrous” (Keeley, 1974, p.
430 326).

431

432

433 **Data Availability**

434 Supplementary material is available on Zenodo:

435 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034213>

436

437

438 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

439 The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal
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441

442

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450

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